

The Effect of Workplace Relationship toward Job Satisfaction of Divine Word Colleges' Employees in Region I, Philippines

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-----ABSTRACT-----

The study was conducted to determine workplace relationship between employer and employees and among employees of Divine Word Colleges in Ilocos Sur, Philippines and its effect on the job satisfaction. Literatures and studies were reviewed, and questionnaires were used to gather the data related to workplace relationship and job satisfaction. The respondents of the study are employees of the colleges of Ilocos region which include Ilocos Sur and Ilocos Norte. The study is a descriptive study involving survey and fact-finding inquiry. Weighted mean and Pearson r were used to determine the workplace relationship and its correlation with job satisfaction. The study found that there is a significant correlation between workplace relationship and job satisfaction. Therefore, the study recommends that management need to monitor and improve workplace relationship between employer and employees and among employees and also improve and monitor factors that affect job satisfaction.

KEYWORDS: Workplace relationship, job satisfaction, employer, employee.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Working relationship is essential requirement for the management and employees to work happily in an office. One would not be too excited to go to the office every day when employee cannot get along with his/her employer and even with his/ her co-employees. One cannot deny the fact that organizational or business performance is also depending on working relationship (Ramjee, 2018). Employee would be excited to perform his/her job when he/she knows that his/her employer and co-employees are around to support him/her. It is a fact that job satisfaction is a result of working relationship and such job satisfaction can affect the organizational performance (Bakotic, 2016). Organizations or business that fail to establish good working relationship tend to have high turnover. It can also affect the mental health of employees causing them not being able to perform their job well (Nadinloyi, Sadeghi, & Hajloo, 2013). People or employee tend to avoid stressful workplace and look for a better place where they can be happy and work comfortably. High turnover will always cause a negative impact on the business particularly productivity. Motivation to work is not all caused by money, but it also depends on the workplace environment. National Business Research Institute (n.d) argues that employee engagement is positively altered when there is good working relationship with other employees. Employees are happy to show up to their work and when they are comfortable to each other and problems at work would become a burden for them because there are other employees who can help. Further when an employee has someone at their place of work considered a "best friend," one of the biggest winners is the company. Based on those research findings, the current research is interested to find out the condition of working environment in terms of employer-employee relationship and employee – employee relationship and how it affects the job satisfaction of employees of Divine Word Colleges in Region I, Philippines.

II. IMPORTANCE OF THE STUDY

The output of this study would help the administrators or managers of Divine Word Colleges to improve its working condition through identification of factors that affect employer-employee, and employee-employer relationship. Beside the administrators, it would be useful for the employees to improve their relationship among the employees.

III. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Understanding Workplace relationship: It cannot be denied that relationship matters in the workplace. Good relationship or bad relationship affect somehow the mood of a person in doing his/her job. Therefore, to maintain a good workplace relationship is important to keep and sustain the excitement of employees to do their job. Employees are working in coordination with other employees and employees are working under the supervision of his/her supervisors. The relationship between employees and between employees and managers affects the feeling and energy and consequently the performance of the person. As it is argued that the level of mood would determine the level of performance and determines how the employees would perform his/her job (Hosie et al 2006, p44 as cited by Essays, 2013, para. 1). Job satisfaction is one of the results of working relationship and such job satisfaction is not just caused by salary (Ram, 2013). Creating such an environment is the job of management and the job of every employees as Patricia (2015, pp. 115-125) argued that management intervention can be helpful in creating friendship at work through social activities inside and outside of the workplace. Beside management intervention, it is also important for the employees try to get along well with other employees.

Ramjee (2018) classified three kinds of workplace relationship and they are management flexibility, employees and co-worker relationship and social relationship. Management flexibility refers to the effort of management to balance the work and family life or personal life. Employees should not be kept from 8-5 within the confinement of the office and without considering the unforeseen event of the employees particularly related to family or personal matters. While co-worker relationship means a harmonious working relationship between employees. Employees should be able to interact with other employees freely within the organization. Finally, social relationship is related to group bonding in which employees feel comfortable with each other and form a coffee group, breakfast or lunch group. He then recommended team building as a solution to those working relationships. Edward (2015) argued that workplace satisfaction is crucial to increase in productivity. The management should give importance to improve workplace satisfaction to enhance performance. Making the employees happy is one of the important jobs of the management. He dismissed the idea that taking hard-nose approach is the best policy for success. While he accepted that structure is also of importance, but it has nothing to do with workplace happiness and individual employee satisfaction. He argued that brain will work better when a person is feeling positive or happy. He then recommended tips to improve workplace satisfaction such as listening to employees, avoiding hovering, allowing creativity and personalization, providing competitive benefits, and respecting employees. Scholars have studied workplace relationship and their studies have revealed that most of employees' difficulties in performing their jobs are a product of working relationship between employee and supervisor. Their studies concluded that most of supervisors are not aware of the impact of their working relationship with the employees on the effectiveness of a subordinate (Childress & Childress 2007, p23 as cited by Essays, 2013). Their study confirms the importance of building good working relationship not only with the supervisors but also with co-employees.

Employee-Employer Relationship: Relationship starts when an employer hires a new employee and signed a contract. All Answers Ltd (2018) as cited from Black's Law Dictionary page 471 (5th ed. 1979) defines employees as a "person in the service of another under any contract of hire, express or implied, oral or written, where the employer has the power or right to control and direct the employee in the material details of how the work is to be performed". Through the contract an employer and employee set promise to be performed in the future as their duty toward each other. It is seen as an agreement between employer and employees that create an obligation between two parties. It is implied that the employee has accepted the offer before he/she signed the contract. However, it is also pointed out that contract does not create productivity or high performance but motivation. Wood et al. (2004, p 355) argued that employers must balance interests such as decreasing wage constraints with a maximization of labor productivity to achieve a profitable and productive employment relationship. Beyond that motivation plays important role in maintaining the relationship and productivity. Thus, motivation is the most difficult factor for employers to effectively manage in the employment relationship. Stone, 2005, p 412). Dubin (1958, p 213) further elaborates on this, noting motivation as "something that moves a person to action, and continues him in the course of action already initiated."

Originally employment relationship was determined by law. The law determines the rights and responsibilities/rules that govern the behavior of both employer and employee which has an impact on how relationship works out. Recent developments particularly in Human Resources Management, the concept of employer-employee relationship has changed which was formally dependent upon interaction of formal legal regulations (Beardwell and Claydon 2007). Traditionally, we have Collective Bargaining. In here, employer and employee representative negotiate matters like pay, terms of employment and working conditions. However, in a recent year there is a trend to shift from traditional collective bargaining to a more individualized method of bargaining ((Henderson 2008, cited by Essays, 2018).

According to Marchington and Wilkinson (2008), the employer-employee relationship indicates employee involvement. Such employee involvement is a form of relations in which employees can participate in decision making that was originally reserved for the management only. Employee-employer relations also indicates conflict and cooperation. Therefore, according to Marchington and Wilkinson (2008) employee -employer relations is important to the success of an organization and failure of it is leading toward its downfall. Success of the organization depends on how well the employee and employer work together. Employer cannot achieve its goal alone but through his/her employees. Therefore, employer needs to develop relationship with the employees and the same to the employees. Employees' job is given by the employer and therefore employees need to develop relationship with his/her employer. Both are relying on each other to conduct the business. According to Schreiner (2018) that managing relationships between employer and employee is vital to business success, as strong relationships can lead to greater employee happiness and even increased productivity. To reap these benefits, keep the dynamics of the employer-employee relationship in mind. While maintaining good relationship with the employee is important, nevertheless, what kind of relationship is the debate. Often time some employers maintain a distance with the employers in order not to cross the line, while others do not. They prefer to be closer to the employees and be friendly with the employees. Two styles do not rule out the best style but what is important to bear in mind is that both parties must know the gap and know their limit.

It has been argued that good employer-employee relationship leads to high performance or productivity. Therefore, it is necessary to maintain good relationship between employer and employees. Halsal (2014, para. 1) suggested several points to consider in promoting good working relationship, namely, mutual respect, mutual reliance, support or nurturing, gratitude and appreciation, open communication, consistent feedback and following through in which the employer delivers what he/she promises to employees. O'Brien (2014) emphasizes the importance of maintaining good relationship as the key to the ultimate success of an organization. He pointed out the benefits of good employer-employee relationship such as increased productivity, employee loyalty, and conflict reduction. Task Management Guide (n.d) explains that the purpose of the employment relationship is to contribute to satisfactory productivity, motivation, and morale of employees as well as to ensure sufficient revenue and profits of employers through preventing and resolving problems which arise out of or affect various work situations.

Employee-employee Relationship: Employee relation is defined as relation between employees in the organization. Any employee who are working in the organization must feel comfortable to deal with each other without hesitation. Such climate is needed for the employees carry out their job happily and this is also important because healthy relation among the employees goes a long way in motivating the employees and increasing their confidence and morale (MSG, n.d). This is not only the job of management, but it is also the job of employees to see to it that employees try their best to adjust to each other and make some compromises if possible. This should be done for the employees to feel excited to enter his work and see his/her co-workers. Work becomes easy if it is shared among all employees and the organization becomes a second home for employees. It encourages cooperation and discourages conflicts among employees and it can also reduce tensions and absenteeism.

Relationship is born over time and it is nurtured, and it naturally grows. It may begin with acquaintance relationship, social relationship and then it is nurtured with friendship. One enters into friendship voluntarily because one has similar or the same goal with the other (Patricia, 2015). The individuals enter this relationship after they have known each other and have shared social and emotional goals. These goals may include feelings of belonging, affection, and intimacy (Lee, 2005, pp. 1-44). Feeling of belongingness, affection and intimacy between individuals must be nurtured and let it grow because once it is neglected, it deteriorates and dies naturally. Therefore, according to Maxwell (2004) developing personal relationship is a serious business that yields dividends to those committed to it. According to the Social Exchange Theory, those feelings must be reciprocated to stay in the relationship. Relationship can never be one sided, both must nurture, invest their time and energy in such relationship Homans (1961). Social exchange theory posits that human relationship are formed using a subjective cost-benefit analysis and the comparison of alternatives.

There are several suggestions on how to improve employee-employee relations at workplace. These include forming team work, encourage individuals to share their ideas with each other, assign target to each team, promote bonding activities, encourage open communication among employees, schedule common meeting or general assembly and organize Christmas parties or birthday celebrations (MSG, n.d). Those the activities in which the management brings the employees together and these can help in strengthening the bond among the employees and ensures that each one is contented and enjoys a healthy relation with each other. Employee relations is not just focused on the relations among employees, but it also includes employee's relations with line managers to established trust-based relationship with employees.

This is based on the belief that a positive climate of employee relations - with high levels of employee involvement, commitment and engagement - can improve business outcomes as well as contribute to employees' well-being (CIPD, 2018).

Job Satisfaction: Job satisfaction is defined as a feeling of the person toward the job which serves as source of motivation. It does not refer to self-satisfaction and contentment, but it is about the feeling on the job. It reflects the simple feeling – state accompanying the attainment of goals or feeling accompanying the attainment of objectives (Green & Heywood, 2008, pp. 710-728). Hoppock (1935) explained job satisfaction as a combination of psychological, physiological and environmental circumstances that cause a person to be satisfied. It is the attitude of the employees toward his job. Hoppock identified three major theories of job satisfaction such as Herzberg's Motivation-Hygiene Theory, Need Fulfillment Theory and Social Reference Group Theory.

Kendal and Hulin (1969) have identified factors that are affecting job satisfaction, and these are first, work itself. This is referring to the working condition. It is the environment provided by the organization which may include amenities, degree of safety, and health and well-being (Bockerman & Ilmakunnas, 2006, pp. 290-302). These are the environmental conditions that affect directly the feeling of employees toward the job. Working conditions may include training, working time, work-life balance (Majid, 2001, pp. 271-291). Second is pay. This refers to the remuneration or salary given to the employees for the work done. Vermandere (2013) in his study argued that employees who are not paid fairly in relation to the workload have negative impact on motivation to work. The study pointed further that employees who were not happy were more inclined to change jobs than the employees who were happy. However, the study also pointed out the other facts that employees were prepared to trade off lower salary against certain benefits, including: a higher retirement payout, a particularly interesting job, a job near home, extra holidays, a (better) company car, extra job security and feeling less controlled at the workplace. Third is promotion. It refers to the advancement in the hierarchy. An employee is shifted to a higher significance and higher compensation (Lazear, 2000, pp. 1346-61). There have been many studies that came to conclusion that job satisfaction is correlated with promotion opportunities (McCausland, Pouliakas & Theodossiou, 2005, pp. 636-59). Fourth is supervision. It is the ability to provide technical assistance and behavioral support to an employee or subordinates. It has been recognized that supervision plays important role in the success or failure of the organization. Beaset (1994, pp. 575-600) argued that the nature and the level of supervision is a factor that may affect satisfaction people derive from their work. The style of supervisory behavior employed by a supervisor is known to be important factor leading to the success or failure of an organization (Adebayo, 2007, pp. 7-12, Eseka, 2009). Supervisory behavior ranges from autocratic, with all the decision made by the supervisor to a more democratic with decision made by the employee or subordinates at the lowest level (Dubrin & Maier, 1993). Fifth is co-employees. This refers to fellow employees who are socially supportive. Ramjee (2018) suggests that when employee feels detached socially and emotionally from other employees in the organization, such situation can cause dissatisfaction. Isolation and loneliness may lead to employee's withdrawal from the job and the organization.

Korman (1977) simplify the five factors presented by Kendal and Hulin (1969) into only two determinant factors of job satisfaction and these are organizational personal variables. Organizational variables may include: first, occupational level. It argues that the higher the level of the job, the greater the satisfaction of the person because it carries with it the prestige and self-control. Second, Job content. When the job is challenging and less repetitiveness with which the task is performed, the greater the satisfaction is. Third, considerate leadership. This refers to leadership style in which supervisor treat employees with consideration. Considerate leadership lead to job satisfaction of employees. Fourth is pay and promotional opportunities. It has been said that pay and promotion opportunities lead to job satisfaction. Lastly is the interaction with the group or co-worker. Korman (1977) explains that good working relationship with co – worker always lead to job satisfaction.

IV. RELATED STUDIES

Under the related studies, we examine previous studies on similar topic about employer-employee relationship and employee-employee relationship and job satisfaction. It seems that there are no many studies yet conducted on the working relationship and job satisfaction, but the following researches are enough to support the argument of the current study. Hong, Hamid, Salleh (2013, pp 26-40) tried to determine factors that affect job satisfaction. Those factors were working environment, pay and salary, fairness and promotion criteria. The study concluded that working environment, pay and salary, and promotion determines the job satisfaction of administrative employees. Pursuing the same interest, Raziq and Maulabakhsh (2015) investigated the relationship between working environment and job satisfaction in the school context. There were five variables identified under working environment and these were working hours, job safety and security, relationship with co-workers and relationship with top management.

This study concluded that working environment affects the job satisfaction of employees. Therefore, they recommended that the management needs to be aware of and improve the workplace environment to increase job satisfaction level of employees. The above findings support the findings of Nanyak (2013). Nanyak studied on the employee's satisfaction, employee relation and job satisfaction and his study revealed the relationship between satisfaction and working environment, salary, compensation, benefits, services, retirement, organizational climate and working environment. Kumari (2011) argued that there is a need to pay attention to different factors that affect working condition and job satisfaction of employees. Bakotic and Babic (2013) strengthen the argument of Kumari that different working condition contributes to job satisfaction. The study argues that workers who work in normal working conditions are more satisfied with working conditions than workers who work under difficult working conditions; in the case of workers who work under difficult working conditions, the working conditions are important factor of their overall job satisfaction.

Working condition is seen as important component of making employees satisfied or dissatisfied. Bakotic and Babic (2013) found in their study that different working condition contributes to job satisfaction. The study argues that workers who work in normal working conditions are more satisfied with working conditions than workers who work under difficult working conditions. In the case of workers who work under difficult working conditions, the working conditions are important factor of their overall job satisfaction. Further studies also revealed that one of the factors contribute to the working condition and job satisfaction is managements' attitude toward employees and the size of a firm. Tansel (2013) went into a study to find out how management attitude toward employees and the firm size affect job satisfaction. The study indicated that management-employee relationships are less satisfactory in the large firms than in the small firms. Job satisfaction levels are lower in large firms. Less satisfactory on management- employee relationships in the large firms contribute to the lower level of job satisfaction of employee.

This study indicates that the more employee the organization has, the more difficult it is to establish good relationship or interpersonal relationship and such situation may affect job satisfaction of employees. Employer-employee relationship seems to be problematic in the large firms compared to small firm. Going into the specific, Frenkel, Sanders and Bednall (2013, pp. 7-29) were motivated to find out if employer-employee relations affect job satisfaction and quit intentions in ten organizations in Australia. Their study led to a conclusion that employer-employee relations were positively related to job satisfaction and quit intentions. Similar study was also conducted by Iwu, Xesha, Slabbert and Nduna, (2014, pp.313-324) on the role employer and employee relationship toward business growth and job satisfaction. The study strengthens the above finding that good relationship between employee and employer is a good predictor toward business and success and job satisfaction. Employer acknowledged that good relationship has contributed toward the success of their business. Harmer and Findlay (n.d) initiated a study of the effect of workplace relationship and job satisfaction. There were three variables that they investigated in the study and these are individual's workplace relationship, direct supervisor relationship and job satisfaction. The study concluded that more than half or 52% of employees' job satisfaction is predicted by the quality of workplace relationships such as individual relationship with their co-worker and their supervisor. National Business Research Institute (n.d) conducted a study on the quality of friendship in the workplace. The study argued that quality friendships at work have a direct link to job satisfaction and engagement. According to research statistics, employee satisfaction skyrockets nearly 50% when a worker develops a close relationship on the job. The study continues to argue that having friends at work benefits not only employees but also the organization as well. Such study has rejected the idea that friendly employees will bond together, creating a mutinous atmosphere of boss-bashing and downright insubordination. Its study explains further that how people succeed, or fail can be based on the support and involvement they have with friends in the workplace.

In conclusion to the above research findings, we argue that though money contributes to job satisfaction (Nunez, 2015) but findings revealed that job satisfaction is not just caused by a single factor such as money but the whole working environment which include employer-employee relationship and employee -employee relationship. The concern of the current study is to find out different aspect of working environment, not only in terms of employer treatment to employees or employer and employees' relationship but also treatment of employees to other employees or employee and employee relationship. Working environment is not just caused by salaries and benefits but working condition as whole, particularly human relationship between management and employee and among employees.

V. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 1: The framework reflects the relationship between employer-employee and employee -employee relationship and job satisfaction. Employer-employee, employee-employee relations are independent variable and job satisfaction is dependent variable.

Employee perceptions of management relations
as influences on job satisfaction and quit intentions
Employee perceptions of management relations
as influences on job satisfaction and quit intentions

Statement of the Problems: The study wants to determine the effect of working relationship between employer-employee and employee-employee toward their job satisfaction, specifically to answer the following questions:

1. What is the working relationship of employer-employee of Divine Word Colleges employees in Region I?
2. What is the working relationship between employee and employee of Divine Word Colleges employees in Region I?
3. What is the job satisfaction of employee?
4. Is there a relationship between working relationship and job satisfaction

Assumption of the Study: The study assumes that working relationship affects the job satisfaction of employees and it can be measured.

Hypothesis: Raziq and Maulabakhsh (2015) investigated the relationship between working environment and job satisfaction in the school context. There were five variables identified under working environment and these were working hours, job safety and security, relationship with co-workers and relationship with top management. The study concluded that working environment affects the job satisfaction of employees. Base on such finding, the current study hypothesizes that employer-employee relationship, employee-employee relationship has impacts on job satisfaction of employees.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study: The study was limited to the employer and employees of Divine Word Colleges in Region I. It limits its investigation only employer-employee, employee-employee relationship and job satisfaction.

Research Methodology: This chapter presents the research design used in this study, data gathering instruments, population, locale of the study, data gathering procedures and statistical treatment of data.

Research Design: Since the study was a quantitative research, thus, the study used descriptive method of research design and fact-finding inquiry to assess and explain the level of employer-employee relationship, employee-employee relationship and its effect on the job satisfaction. According to Jewel, et.al (2010), descriptive research is used to organize, and describe the characteristics of the data collected.

Locale of the Study : The study was conducted in the Divine Word Colleges in Region I, which includes Divine Word College of Vigan, and Divine Word College of Laoag. These colleges are in Ilocos Sur, and Ilocos Norte.

Population: The population of the study was taken from all employees working in these colleges. There were 270 employees taken as respondents of the study. Since the population of the study was small, so the total enumeration was used in which all employees of the three colleges were taken as the respondents of the study. Total enumeration was taken based on the judgment of the researcher to meet the objective of the study.

VI. DATA GATHERING INSTRUMENTS

The study utilized questionnaires. The questionnaires were constructed by the researcher and validated by expert to judge its content. They were distributed to employees of the Divine Word Colleges. The questionnaires were consisted of two parts. First part is employer-employee relationship. The second part is employee-employee relationship. The first part and second part of the questionnaires were adapted from Raziq and Maulabakhsh (2015). Third part is job satisfaction. The content job satisfaction questionnaires were based on the job satisfaction dimension presented by Kendal and Hulin (1969) and Korman (1977).

Data Gathering Procedures: In the process of data gathering, the researcher sent letters to the Presidents of the two colleges requesting the Presidents to allow the researcher to flow his questionnaires in his college. The researcher personally met the Presidents and employees and requested them to answer the questionnaires. The retrieval of questionnaires was arranged between the President’s representative and the researcher with the help of employees and faculty of the three colleges. Some inquiries were done after tabulation and interpretation of data to validate the finding through research questionnaires.

Statistical Treatment of Data: In consistent with the study as descriptive research, therefore descriptive statistics was used to measure frequency distribution and percentage and the weighted mean. The weighted mean was used to assess the employees’ perception of organizational politics and job satisfaction. To determine the relationships between employer-employee relationship, employee-employee relationship and job satisfaction, **Pearson r** was used. The following ranges of values with their descriptive interpretation were used:

Scale	Range of Weighted means	Descriptive interpretation
5	4.21-5.00	Very good /Very satisfied
4	3.41-4.20	Good/satisfied
3	2.61-3.40	Somewhat good/Somewhat satisfied
2	1.81-2.60	Bad/Dissatisfied
1	1.00-1.80	Very bad/ Very dissatisfied

Findings: The findings of the study are presented here bellow according to the statement of the problems.

1. What is the working relationship of employer-employee of Divine Word Colleges employees in Region I?

Table 1: Employer-Employee Relationship

	X	DR
1. There is a mutual relationship between supervisors and subordinates	3.92	Good/satisfied
2. Supervisors rely on their subordinates and subordinates rely on their supervisors.	3.77	Good/satisfied
3. Supervisors communicate openly with their subordinates and the same subordinates communicate openly with their supervisors	3.80	Good/satisfied
4. Supervisors support their subordinates and subordinates support their supervisors	3.70	Good/satisfied
5. Supervisors feel free to give feedback to their subordinates and subordinates feel free to give feedback to their supervisors	3.55	Good/satisfied
6. Supervisors often express gratitude to their subordinates and subordinates also often express gratitude toward their supervisor	3.68	Good/satisfied
7. Supervisors follow through what they have promised to their subordinates and subordinates too follow through what they have promised to their supervisors	3.66	Good/satisfied
8. Supervisors allow subordinates to participate in decision - making and subordinates can make their own decisions	3.60	Good/satisfied
9. The supervisor can get the cooperation of subordinates easily and subordinates can get the cooperation of supervisors easily	3.59	Good/satisfied
Overall	3.70	Good/satisfied

Legends:

- 4.21-5.00 *Very good /Very satisfied*
- 3.41-4.20 *Good/satisfied*
- 2.61-3.40 *Somewhat good/Somewhat satisfied*
- 1.81-2.60 *Bad/Dissatisfied*
- 1.00-1.80 *Very bad/ Very dissatisfied*

As it is deduced from the table, the result indicates that overall there is a good relationship between employer and employees as reflected by its overall mean of 3.70 which is interpreted as good or satisfied. Taken them singly, the results also indicate that there is a good working relationship between employer and employees particularly in terms of mutual relationship (3.92), reliance (3.77), communication (3.80), support (3.70), giving feedbacks (3.55), expression of gratitude (3.68), participation in decision making (3.68), follow up promises (3.66), and cooperation (3.59).

2. What is the working relationship between employee and employee of Divine Word Colleges employees in Region I?

Table2: Employee-Employee Relationship

Employee-employee Relationship		
	X	DR
1. There is a mutual respect among employees	3.91	Good/Satisfied
2. Employees can depend on each other	3.75	Good/satisfied
3. Employees can easily get the cooperation of other employees in community programs or activities	3.76	Good/satisfied
4. Employees can communicate openly to other employees without hesitation	3.61	Good/satisfied
5. Employees often help one another in solving problems they encounter in the workplace	3.61	Good/satisfied
6. Employees always show respect to their fellow employees	3.77	Good/satisfied
7. Employees support one another whenever there is a need for support	3.73	Good/satisfied
8. Employees often give feedback to their fellow employees even it is negative feedbacks	3.53	Good/satisfied
9. Employees also often express gratitude to their fellow employees after they are helped	3.80	Good/satisfied
Overall	3.72	Good/satisfied

Legends:

- 4.21-5.00 *Very good /Very satisfied*
- 3.41-4.20 *Good/satisfied*
- 2.61-3.40 *Somewhat good/Somewhat satisfied*
- 1.81-2.60 *Bad/Dissatisfied*
- 1.00-1.80 *Very bad/ Very dissatisfied*

Based on the data gathered and the computed mean, overall, there is a good relationship between employee and employee as pointed out by its overall mean of 3.72 which is interpreted as good or satisfied. Even when taking them singly, all questions under this variable are evaluated as good particularly related to mutual respect among employees (3.91), dependence (reliance) on each other (3.75), cooperation (3.76), good communication (3.61), helping one another (3.61), respect each other (3.77), support one another (3.73), give feedback to one another (3.53), and expressing gratitude toward one another (3.80).

3. 3. What is the job satisfaction of employee?

Table 3: Job Satisfaction of Employees

Job Satisfaction	X	DR
1. I am satisfied with my supervisors	3.88	Good/satisfied
2. I am satisfied with my workload	3.97	Good/satisfied
3. I am satisfied with my job security	3.87	Good/satisfied
4. I am satisfied with the nature of my work	3.97	Good/satisfied
5. I am satisfied with my salary	3.11	Somewhat Good/Somewhat Satisfied
6. I am satisfied with working hours	3.69	Good/satisfied
7. I am satisfied with my co – employees	3.85	Good/satisfied
8. I am satisfied with the treatment from supervisors	3.74	Good/satisfied
9. I am satisfied because the job gives meaning to me	4.08	Good/satisfied
10. I am satisfied because there is opportunity for promotion	3.67	Good/satisfied
Overall	3.78	Good/satisfied

Legends

- 4.21-5.00 *Very good /Very satisfied*
- 3.41-4.20 *Good/satisfied*
- 2.61-3.40 *Somewhat good/Somewhat satisfied*
- 1.81-2.60 *Bad/Dissatisfied*
- 1.00-1.80 *Very bad/ Very dissatisfied*

As indicated in the table, it shows that overall, the employees are satisfied with their job as indicated by its overall mean rating of 3.78 which is interpreted as satisfied. Even if taking them singly, all questions were rated within the same evaluation that employees are satisfied with their job particularly with their superiors (3.88), with their workload (3.97), job security (3.87), the nature of their work (3.97), working hours (3.69), co-employees (3.85), treatment from superiors (3.74), the job itself as a source of meaning (4.08), and opportunity for promotion (3.67). There was only one question which was rated somewhat satisfied along salary (3.11).

4. 4. Is there a relationship between working relationship and job satisfaction?

Table 4: The relationship between working relationship and job satisfaction

	Job Satisfaction
Employee-Employee	0.5000*
Employer-employee	0.5601*
As a whole	0.5301*

*Significant at .05 level

As it is indicated in the correlation table, it shows that as a whole there is a significant correlation between workplace relationship particularly between employee and employee and between employer and employee and job satisfaction at .05 level of significance. Even when taking them singly, the two variables have a significant correlation with job satisfaction.

V. CONCLUSION

The study concludes that overall there is a good workplace relationship between employer and employee and even among employees of Divine Word Colleges in Ilocos Region. In terms of its correlation with job satisfaction, the study showed that good workplace relationship is significantly correlated to job satisfaction. It just manifests that managing good workplace relationship is a key contributing factor to increase job satisfaction and consequently increase performance and productivity.

Recommendation : Hong, Hamid, Salleh (2013, pp 26-40) have conducted like this study to determine factors that affect job satisfaction. Those factors were working environment, pay and salary, fairness and promotion criteria. The study concluded that working environment, pay and salary, and promotion determines the job satisfaction of administrative employees. The current study has found similar finding that good workplace relationship significantly contributes to job satisfaction and therefore the following recommendations are drawn:

1. There is a need to monitor and improve workplace relationship between employer and employee and among employees. Those factors to be monitored and improved are communication between employer and employee and among employees, participation in decision making, help and support from both sides, respect and fair treatment from both sides, honest feedbacks from both sides, trustworthiness and cooperation.
2. The management need to monitor and improve workplace relationship among employees through programs or activity that promote respect toward fellow workers, cooperation, communication, help and support among employees and honest feedbacks among employees.
3. In terms of job satisfaction, the management need to focus on improving factors that are crucial to job satisfaction such as salary, workloads, job security, working hours, fair treatment from management, and promotion to those who deserve.

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